

A Review on the Utilization of Coral Aggregate and Polypropylene Fiber in High Strength Concrete

Yatik Rajput¹, Nirav Patel²

¹*Civil Engineering, Parul University*

²*Civil Engineering, Parul University*

Abstract— This review concentrates on the use of polypropylene fibers (PPF) and coral aggregate (CA) in the growth of high-strength concrete (HSC), observes both mechanical properties and environmental suggestions. Polypropylene fibres are renowned for improving concrete's tensile strength, durability, and resistance to cracking. Coral aggregate, obtained from marine environments, offers a sustainable replacement to standard aggregates, especially in offshore regions. The review combines experimental data on the interaction between these materials, highlighting developments in compressive and tensile strength when integrated into HSC (high strength concrete). The effect of changing fiber content and coral aggregate ratios on the structural integrity, durability, and workability of HSC is also conferred. Despite considerable advantages, challenges such as environmental study considering coral harvesting and potential workability concerns with fiber incorporation are noted. Future exploration is suggested, highlighting the requirement for optimizing mix designs and developing eco-friendly obtaining strategies for coral aggregates. This review highlights the prospective of using polypropylene fibres and coral aggregates in sustainable high-strength concrete implementation, especially in marine and coastal construction.

Keywords— High-Strength Concrete (HSC), Polypropylene Fibres (PPF), Coral Aggregate (CA), Tensile Strength, Compressive Strength

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent construction, high-strength concrete (HSC) has become a key material because of its excellent mechanical properties, durability, and resistance to severe environmental circumstances. The construction industry continuously looks for to improve concrete's performance by integrating numerous materials and fibers, both synthetic and natural, that enhance its structural integrity and durability. One such synthetic fiber, polypropylene, has grown courtesy for its capability to increase the tensile strength and decrease cracking in concrete structures. Concurrently, there is rising concern in exploiting replacement, more sustainable aggregates such as coral aggregate (CA), particularly in seaside regions where usual aggregates may be scarce. Polypropylene Fibres (PPF) are increasingly being used in high-strength concrete for many purposes. Polypropylene fibres are known to develop the crack resistance, ductility, and toughness of concrete, while also reducing shrinkage cracking during the curing process. These fibres can resist harsh environmental conditions and resist chemical corrosion, making them perfect for use in concrete structures subjected to harsh environments. In the view of high-strength concrete, polypropylene fibres play a vital role in improving the tensile strength and controlling the widening of microcracks, which are common in standard concrete mixes.

Coral Aggregate (CA), a natural and abundant resource in coastal and marine environments, presents a promising option to traditional coarse aggregates like gravel and crushed stone. Coral aggregates, originated from coral reefs, have a porous structure, making them lightweight compared to regular aggregates. This lightweight nature, along with the material's relative abundance in coastal regions, offers potential cost savings and sustainability benefits, especially for island and coastal infrastructure projects. However, coral aggregates also pose some challenges due to their lower compressive strength and possible reactivity in certain environments. Additionally, the environmental impact of coral mining, especially regarding the degradation of marine ecosystems, remains a critical concern that demands further exploration.

Mixing polypropylene fibres with coral aggregate in high-strength concrete represents a novel approach to achieving a balance between enhanced mechanical performance and sustainability. Recent studies indicate that integrating these two materials can theoretically improve the compressive and tensile strength of high-strength concrete, as well as its durability in marine and coastal environments. Polypropylene fibres provide the necessary reinforcement to compensate for the lower strength of coral aggregates, leads to a more durable and resilient concrete mix. Moreover, the use of coral aggregate, especially in regions where traditional aggregates are scarce or expensive, can considerably reduce construction costs and project timelines.

Even though these benefits, challenges remain in optimizing the mix design for high-strength concrete using polypropylene fibres and coral aggregates. The brittle nature of coral aggregate and the optimal quantity of polypropylene fibres need to be carefully regulated to ensure the best performance outcomes. The long-term durability of such concrete mixes in destructive environments, such as those with high sulfate or chloride exposure, also requires further investigation. Additionally, the environmental implications of coral extraction require the development of sustainable practices to minimize ecological damage.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Hua Zhang, Xinyue Liu, Linjian Ma, Zeng Li [1] The mechanical properties of CASC (coral aggregate concrete) with inserted PP (polypropylene) fibers were explored through quasi static compressive test and SHPB (split Hopkinson pressure bar) test. The static compressive strength of CASC (coral aggregate concrete) rises first and then descends with the increasing PP fiber content. While the static compressive strength of CASC was evidently enhanced with the higher proportion of natural gravel among the coarse aggregate. The addition of PP fiber can obviously enhance the peak toughness and ultimate toughness of CASC, whereas, when the PP fiber content exceeds 3 kg/m, toughness will be declined. Adding appropriate content of PP fibers to the CASC or replacing coral aggregate with appropriate amount of gravel can effectively improve the impact strength and toughness of CASC, which provides a theoretical basis of the future development of the island construction.

Hongwei Han, Gongwen Gao, Yu Li, Dongxu Hou, Yudong Han [2] SCECC (seawater coral sand engineered cementitious composites) exhibits a pronounced early strength. The compressive strength of the 7-day specimen can achieve more than 78.50% of that observed in the 28-day specimen. As the PVA fiber volume fraction increases, the flexural strength and fracture energy of the material tend to increase significantly, the maximum flexural strength and fracture energy of the 28-day specimen could reach 13.43 MPa and 1973.70 J/m², respectively. The delay in microcrack formation and prevention of crack propagation, which improves deformability of the material by the properties of fibre. When the volume fraction of PVA fiber exceeded 1.150% the restraint of cracks by fiber became more pronounced. The PVA fibers spanning the cracks continues carrying and transmitting tensile forces through a robust bridging action, reveals a notable strain-hardening characteristic to the specimen as per splitting tensile test.

Jianhua Guo, Yumei Wang b, Zhiheng Deng, Ping Chang [3] The intermediate-length columns of coral concrete-filled aluminium alloy tube exhibit good compressive performance, with a significant combined effect between the aluminium alloy tube and the core concrete. Deformation ductility, the compressive stiffness and ultimate load-carrying capacity of all specimens decrease as increase in the section width-to-thickness ratio (B/t). The ultimate load-carrying capacity and deformation ductility of the specimens gradually decrease, though the extent of flexural deformation significantly increases as the aspect ratio of the column (L/B) increases, under the condition that end-zone failure does not occur.

Hao LIU, Huamei YANG, Houzhen WEI, Jining YU, Qingshan MENG, Rongtao YAN [4] Investigation done on the mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of magnesium potassium phosphate cement-based CS mortar and RS mortar. With increasing M/P (mass ratio of MgO to KH₂ PO₄), w/b (mass ratio of water to MKPC), and borax (mass ratio of borax to MgO) content, the compressive strength of MKPC (magnesium potassium phosphate cement) CS mortar at different curing times first increased and then decreased.

Bai Zhanga, Hui Penga, Teng Xiong, Hong Zhu [5] The mechanical properties of GPCAC and CAC under seawater drying-wetting cycles were explored, and their degradation mechanisms in terms of mechanical characteristics were estimated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The compressive strength of MKPC CS mortar remained stable after long-term immersion in water and Na₂ SO₄ solution. In addition, after long-term immersion in Na₂ SO₄ solution, the compressive strength increased: by 12.5% after 56 d and 10.6% after 90 d. When subjected to 60C seawater corrosion in drying-wetting cycles for 12months, the cubic compressive strength, elastic modulus, and axial compressive strength of CAC degraded by 14.4%, 13.0%, and 16.9%, respectively, while those of GPCAC only reduced by 5.4%, 11.8%, and 3.1%, respectively. In this paper corrosion age and corrosion temperature on the compressive strength, stress strain curves, and elastic modulus for CAC and GPCAC under drying-wetting cycles of seawater were analyzed. GPCAC (geopolymer-based seawater coral aggregate concrete) exhibited better seawater attack resistance than CAC after being subjected to a sea water drying wetting cycle environment. The excellent pore structure, dense microstructure, and stabilized hydration products of geopolymers are the reasons for their better performance against seawater environments than cement-based materials. The failure modes for all GPCAC and CAC specimens were featured by the broken CAs originating from their low strength and high brittle ness. As the exposure temperature and time upgraded, the microcracks from the surface concrete on the specimens at failure increased and the angle of the main cracks inclined to the axial direction lowered. After suffering from the corrosive condition of seawater, the microstructural changes at aggregate-slurry matrix interfaces inside the specimens were not apparent, but their reaction products underwent certain transformations. When the specimens experienced seawater solution attacks, C-(A)-S-H gels in reaction products for geopolymer and cement pastes were comparatively stabilized. Nevertheless, gypsum and Ca(OH)₂ in cement pastes were comparatively unstable and susceptible to chemical reactions with corrosive ions (e.g. Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻) in seawater, forming ettringite or Friedel's salt. These chemical reactions weakened the strength and compactness for the slurry matrix inside the structure, thereby resulting in a bigger strength deterioration rate in CAC than in GPCAC. The results pointed out that GPCAC exhibited better resistance to seawater attack than CAC after being subjected to seawater drying-wetting cycle environments.

Daming Luo, Meng Zhou, Fan Li, Ditao Niu [6] The study conducted for analyzation & comparison of coral aggregate chloride ion content prediction model based on CART, SVM, and XGBoost under the coupling of multiple factors & drying-wetting cycles. The chloride ion content distribution curve of coral aggregate concrete specimens subjected to drying-wetting

cycles in a 3.5% NaCl solution and 3.5% NaCl+5% Na₂SO₄ solution shows an initial increase followed by a subsequent decrease along the depth. Under the coupling erosion of sulfate and chloride salts, the erosion effect on concrete exhibits a “superimposed effect”, whereby the presence of SO₄²⁻ hinders Cl⁻ transport initially and accelerates it later. During the wet stage, SO₄²⁻ will accelerate the transition of corrosion to the internal pores, cracks, and interface transition zone of the concrete. Conversely, during the dry stage, Na₂SO₄ crystallization occurs due to water evaporation, thereby accelerating concrete deterioration. The result shows that CART, SVR, and XGBoost algorithms, reveals high prediction accuracy. The compressive strength and relative dynamic elastic modulus of coral aggregate concrete can be improved, along with its resistance to Cl⁻ corrosion, through the addition of mineral admixtures. SO reacts with cement hydration products to produce ettringite and gypsum, which hinder further Cl⁻ corrosion during the early stage of erosion.

Bai Zhang, Hong Zhu, Teng Xiong, Hui Peng [7] The effects of the type of FRP bars (GFRP, BFRP, and CFRP bars), the longitudinal reinforcement ratio (0.48–1.12%), and the diameter of FRP bars (8 and 10 mm) on the flexural behavior of CAC and AACAC (alkali-activated coral aggregate concrete) beams were evaluated. Crack height and crack spacing gradually lowered as well as the number of cracks in AACAC beams increased with an increase in reinforcement ratio as per the results. The mid-span deflection and the strength utilization of internal FRP bars decreased while the cracking load, ultimate load, and slope of load–deflection curves at the ascending stage (i.e., flexural stiffness) exerted a significant improvement as in increase in reinforcement ratio.

Wen Zhou, Peng Feng, Hongwei Lin [8] The study carried out on the mechanical behavior of CAC subjected to uniaxial loading, conventional triaxial loading and true triaxial loading. The failure modes under several loading situations were deliberated, and constitutive models were recommended. In uniaxial compression, the failure mode of CAC (coral aggregate concrete) was similar to that of LAC (light weight aggregate concrete), which was more brittle than the failure of NAC (normal aggregate concrete). The coral coarse aggregates were completely broken at the failure surfaces. The stress–strain behavior of CAC under uniaxial compression could not be satisfactorily portrayed by the present models for NAC. In the conventional triaxial tests, CAC showed more damage than NAC. Due to the presence of lateral pressure, both the peak strength and the post peak strength were significantly enhanced with larger fracture strain. Compared with NAC, CAC had a lower strength improvement under the same confining pressure.

Daguan Huang, Xiufei Li, Li Su, Jianbo Tian, Zhanwei Zhao [9] To calculate the chloride concentration distribution under different erosion environments chloride diffusion model was used and to verify the accuracy of the diffusion model the experimental values were compared and analysed. Theoretical basis for the durability design and life prediction of coral aggregate concrete under extremely hot and humid marine environments could provide by establishment of the model. During a sulfate attack, the degree of damage was quantified as the ratio of the eroded concrete’s cross-sectional area to the total concrete area. The correlation between the relative chloride diffusion coefficient and the extent of damage was determined, and the damage from sulfate attack was incorporated into the chloride diffusion model.

Hao Shi, Qing Wu, RongRong Yin, Muhammad Akbar, Ning Yang [10] Investigation done on the diffusion of sulfate ions in coral seawater concrete under the mechanism of the wetting drying cycle of sulfate solution, & test conducted on coral concrete at different depths under different cycles for the concentration of sulfate ions. By the use of COMSOL software finite-element numerical simulations were carried out. The sulfate ion concentration in the concrete at the same depth as well as erosion depth increased steadily with time as per the results. The numerical simulations successfully reproduced the diffusion of sulfate ions in coral seawater concrete under the mechanism of the wetting–drying cycle of sulfate solutions.

Dong Wang, Baifu Luo, Qinqin Feng, Wei Zhang [11] The compressive strength of PAACC reached about 55% that of AAG, ranging between 35 and 46MPa at 28 days, with low chloride content (0.006%–0.016%), meeting the requirements for most marine structures. With the decreasing size distribution of CA, the compressive strength increases of PAACC, that is, the CA in PAACC may be said to be acting as filling material that may be regarded as empty holes. The prewetting of water released by CA during the curing process speeds up the early strength development of PAACC, thus bringing about its ultimate compressive strength improvement.

Xiaofei Zhang, Zhengliang Dong [12] The design strength of C30 polypropylene fiber (PF) coral concrete as the object of study, curing at 7d, 14d, 21d, 28d, total 20 groups of different specimens were prepared to explore its mechanical properties experimental investigation carried out. To study the microstructure of coral aggregate concrete, analysis of PF enhancement and modification mechanism of coral concrete FE SEM scanning electron microscopy were used. The experimental results show that PF can increase the compressive and tensile strength of coral concrete to different degrees, and there is an optimal mixing ratio of PF, and the mechanical properties of coral concrete will gradually decrease when the mixing ratio of PF varies from the optimal ratio. The damage morphology of coral concrete specimens does not affected by the age of curing, and as we compare the ordinary specimens the damage morphology of the fiber-doped specimens is significantly improved. With the gradual increase of PF doping ratio, the compressive strength of the specimens showed a trend of increasing and then decreasing. The minimum peak growth rate of 39.30% compressive strength appeared in the 0.15% fiber doping at 28d of maintenance. When the curing age is 7 d, the growth rate of compressive strength of PF on CAC is 24.58%, 32.40%, 28.13% and 11.84%, which are greater than 11.67%, 12.62%, 13.49% and 3.38% when the curing age is 28 d.

Lijuan Zhang, Xiang Li, Changbin Li, Jun Zhao [13] Effects of Steel fiber (0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5%) and polypropylene fiber (0.9 kg/m³, 1.2 kg/m³ and 1.5kg/m³) on the properties of FRAC, including compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, the splitting tensile load–displacement curve, the tensile toughness index, flexural strength, the load–deflection curve, and the flexural toughness index examined. The enhancement of the crack resistance, tensile toughness, and flexural toughness obtained by adding steel fiber to the FRAC is more significant than that obtained by adding polypropylene fiber. The compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and flexural strength of fiber-reinforced FRAC were remarkably enhanced compared with those of ordinary FRAC, and the maximum increase was 56.9%, 113.3%, and 217.0%, respectively.

Rajai Al-Rousan, Bara'a R. Alnemrawi [14] The bending behavior of reinforced concrete (RC) slabs with polypropylene fibers (PF) under the effect of different opening ratios were examined by the nonlinear finite element analysis (NLFEA) method. The effect of different square opening ratios between 0 and 24% and PF volume percentage ranging between 0 to 1% with 0.1% increments included in the investigation. The slab's behavior was deliberated which focuses on different structural performance characteristics like ductility, using energy-based approaches and deflection-based approaches, cracking, stiffness (initial and yielding) and ultimate load strength. It was observed that the presence of PFs at different percentages has a notable effect on the behavior of RC slabs with small openings (less than 2% opening ratio) compared to slabs with larger opening sizes the acceptable improvements can be seen in slabs with small opening sizes. Consequently, regular steel rebars for RC slabs with small openings, PF could be used as a replacement. By the use of 0.3, 0.6, and 0.9% of PF improves its ability to stabilize the generated cracks by 5, 13, and 16%. In addition, increasing the PF percentage increases the resulting crack-opening value at failure due to the provided stabilization effect, in addition to increasing the system's ability to sustain loads.

Kemal Karakuzu, Suleyman Ozen, Aden Dogangun [15] The study conducted to enhance the mechanical and durability properties of Khorasan mortar (type of lime-based mortar), using shrinkage reducing admixture (SRA) and polypropylene fiber. Three series of mixtures were prepared to the control mixture without fiber and chemical admixture. The first series contains 0.4–0.6–0.8% polypropylene fiber by total volume; the second series contains SRA at the 0.05–0.1–0.15% by binder weight; the third series consists of mixtures containing both fiber and the SRA. The results show that 90 day flexural and compressive strength values for all mixtures were lower than the 28-day results. The flexural and compressive strengths of the specimens were observed to be decreased compared to the control mixture due to the increase in the fiber utilization ratio in the mortar mixtures, the formation of voids and the negative effect of fiber-matrix adhesion.

Jiuyang Li, Xinmei Fan, Yuepeng Zhu, Jingwei Luo [16] Investigation done on the effect of three different shapes of polypropylene fiber on the mechanical properties of concrete at different dosages. Cubic compressive ability test, split tensile ability test, and flexural ability test were conducted on polypropylene fiber concrete to analyze the effect of PPF on compressive ability, tensile compression ratio, and flexural compression ratio. The main factor affecting the tensile/compression ratio of concrete is the dosage of PPF. Within 0~0.60%, the tensile and compression ratios of the three PPF-reinforced concrete gradually increase with the rising of PPF. Combined with fiber shape and cost, 0.60% wavy PPF has the most favourable effect on the split tensile strength of concrete, which is 69.94% bigger than that of ordinary concrete. The concrete tensile & compression ratio is mainly affected by the mixing amount of polypropylene fibers.

III. CONCLUSION

The addition of polypropylene fibres (PPF) and coral aggregate (CA) into high-strength concrete (HSC) signifies a promising development in the field of sustainable construction materials for coastal and marine purposes. Polypropylene fibres have established their effectiveness in enhancing the mechanical properties of concrete, specifically in improving tensile strength, reducing crack formation and increasing durability. Coral aggregate suggests an eco-friendly alternative to traditional aggregates, particularly in regions where natural resources is limited.

The studies revealed that polypropylene fibres can significantly improves toughness, crack resistance the tensile strength of coral aggregate concrete, thereby compensating for the essential weaknesses of coral aggregate, such as its lower compressive strength and brittleness. Additionally, the use of coral aggregate helps reduce the overall weight of the concrete, making it suitable for applications where lightweight materials are required. However, the porous nature of coral aggregate can affect the concrete's workability, requiring careful adjustment of the water-cement ratio and other mix components. Since an environmental perspective, using coral aggregate originated from waste or non-living coral sources can promote sustainability efforts by reducing the demand for land-based aggregates and restrains environmental degradation. However, concerns remain about the impact of large-scale coral mining on ecosystems, calling for stricter regulations and research into alternative sources and synthetic aggregates.

The synergy between polypropylene fibres and coral aggregate has the potential to create a concrete material that is both structurally robust and environmentally sustainable. This combination holds certain promise for infrastructure in coastal and marine environments, where both corrosion resistance and sustainability are critical. Despite the promising results, several challenges remain same, including optimizing the mix design to ensure maximum strength and durability, addressing workability issues, and conducts long-term studies to assess the material's performance under harsh environmental conditions. Future research should focus on improving the mix proportions, exploring hybrid reinforcement techniques, and assessing the long-term durability of PPF (polypropylene fiber)-CA (coral aggregate) concrete under various environmental stressors.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hua Zhang, Xinyue Liu, Linjian Ma, Zeng Li. "Effects of polypropylene fibers and aggregate contents on the impact performance of coral aggregate concrete", *Journal of Building Engineering*, Vol. 81 (2023)
- [2] Hongwei Han, Gongwen Gao, Yu Li, Dongxu Hou, Yudong Han, "Effect of PVA Fiber on the Mechanical Properties of Seawater Coral Sand Engineered Cementitious Composites", *Materials*, Vol. 17(6), 2024
- [3] Jianhua Guo, Yumei Wang b, Zhiheng Deng, Ping Chang, "Research on the axial compression performance of coral concrete-filled aluminum alloy tube columns", *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, Vol. 20 (2024)
- [4] Hao LIU, Huamei YANG, Houzhen WEI, Jining YU, Qingshan MENG, Rongtao YAN, "Effect of coral sand on the mechanical properties and hydration mechanism of magnesium potassium phosphate cement mortar", *Journal of Zhejiang University-Science A*, Vol. 25, pages 116–129 (2023)
- [5] Bai Zhanga, Hui Penga, Teng Xiong, Hong Zhu, "Towards enhancing the durability of seawater coral aggregate concrete under drying-wetting cycles with slag-based geopolymers", *Journal of Sustainable Cement-Based Materials*, Vol. 13(3), 2023
- [6] Daming Luo, Meng Zhou, Fan Li, Ditao Niu, "Chloride ion transport in coral aggregate concrete subjected to coupled erosion by sulfate and chloride salts in drying-wetting cycles", *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, Vol. 30, p. 3251-3267, 2024
- [7] Bai Zhang, Hong Zhu, Teng Xiong, Hui Peng, "Flexural behavior of FRP bars reinforced seawater coral aggregate concrete beams incorporating alkali-activated materials", Vol. 57(26), 2024
- [8] Wen Zhou, Peng Feng, Hongwei Lin, "Constitutive relations of coral aggregate concrete under uniaxial and triaxial compression", *Construction and Building Materials*, Vol. 251, 2020
- [9] Dagan Huang, Xiufei Li, Li Su, Jianbo Tian, Zhanwei Zhao "Chloride diffusion model in coral aggregate concrete Under extremely hot and humid marine environments", *Ceramics-Silikaty*, 2024
- [10] Hao Shi, Qing Wu, RongRong Yin, Muhammad Akbar, Ning Yang "Diffusion law of sulfate ions in coral aggregate seawater concrete in the marine environment", *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, Vol. 43(1) 2024
- [11] Dong Wang, Baifu Luo, Qinqin Feng, Wei Zhang, "Development of Preplaced Alkali - Activated Coral Concrete for a Marine Environment", *ASCE*, Vol. 36(1) 2023
- [12] Xiaofei Zhang, Zhengliang Dong, "Study on the Effect of Polypropylene Fibres on the Mechanical and Structural Properties of Early Age Coral Concrete", *ICCASE*, 2024
- [13] Lijuan Zhang, Xiang Li, Changbin Li, Jun Zhao, "Mechanical Properties of Fully Recycled Aggregate Concrete Reinforced with Steel Fiber and Polypropylene Fiber", *Materials*, Vol. 17(5), 2024
- [14] Rajai Al-Rousan, Bara'a R. Alnemrawi, "NLFEA of the Behavior of Polypropylene Fiber-Reinforced Concrete Slabs with Square Opening", *Buildings*, Vol. 14(2), 2024
- [15] Kemal Karakuzu, Suleyman Ozen, Aden Dogangun, "Effects of Shrinkage Reducing Admixture and Polypropylene Fiber Utilization on Some Fresh State, Mechanical and Durability Properties of Khorasan Mortar", *International journal of architectural heritage*, Vol. 18(1), 2022
- [16] Jiuyang Li, Xinmei Fan, Yuepeng Zhu, Jingwei Luo, "Study on the effect of polypropylene fiber shape and admixture on the mechanical properties of concrete", *Journal of Physics*, Vol. 2808 (2023)